

Breaking the Barrier: Why India Must Talk about IBS

India's IBS Awakening

Shraddha Saroj,^{1*} Parvati², Kalpna Gupta¹, Sumit Rungta³

^{1*}*Research Scholar (SRF), Food Science and Nutrition, Department of Home Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India.*

²*Diet Counsellor, District Hospital, Ayodhya, Uttar Pradesh, India.*

¹*Professor, Human Development, Department of Home Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India*

³*Associate Professor, Department of Gastroenterology (Head), King George Medical University, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India*

Corresponding author:

Shraddha Saroj, Pursuing PhD (Senior Research Fellow), Food Science and Nutrition, Department of Home science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221005

Abstract:

Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) is a common gastrointestinal disorder that affects the large intestine. It causes symptoms like abdominal pain, bloating, gas, diarrhoea, and constipation. This article highlights the social and psychological challenges faced by people suffering from IBS with special reference to India. It focuses on the need to address the stigma that prevents open discussion and timely management. With about 4-7% of the people affected the article talks about the need for initiating awareness campaigns throughout the country. Overall, it calls for a more empathetic, informed attitude towards IBS to improve diagnosis, care and quality of life.

Keywords: Irritable bowel syndrome, India, World, Women, Government

World Scenario:

The concept of health literacy involves peoples knowledge, opinions and motivation to analyse, access and apply health related information to take decisions regarding prevention against diseases and health promotion¹. A study done in 2023 has reported that 9 out of 10 individuals lack health literacy which poses a major challenge in India². Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), a chronic health issue associated with gut-brain axis, which is characterized by bloating, distention, diarrhoea, constipation³, irregular stool frequency etc. IBS is facing worldwide awareness challenge as there are no significant anatomical changes or pathological indicators to report it⁴. IBS is diagnosed by exclusion not by any specific test. Despite several studies about the psychological issues, nutrition guidelines, gut microbiota and economic effect, there are hardly any study regarding the public awareness about IBS¹. Many patients have reported that they feel embarrassed⁴ while talking about the gastrointestinal symptoms. Unlike diabetes or cancer, there are rarely any efforts from the media for normalizing IBS talks. There are hardly any awareness campaigns. Moreover, IBS is often regarded as a 'minor problem' or 'not real issue' by general population. One of the major causes for this misconception is the overlapping or mimicking effect of the IBS symptoms with other functional diseases associated with gut such as lactose intolerance, dyspepsia⁵, inflammatory bowel disease to name a few. Many IBS patients have also informed that the health care providers don't explain clearly about IBS, which may be due to lack of time for each patient or they may not feel it necessary as it's not regarded as a life-threatening issue⁶. Cultural influence⁷ may make it even more challenging to discuss about digestive issues as it may be considered inappropriate in some orthodox societies. Extreme gender disparities in some societies may also be one of the reasons for higher IBS prevalence

among the females. Many studies also indicated that IBS is underreported in general as people think it's a stress or diet related issue and thus don't visit a health care provider ⁸.

Specific hurdles with reference to India:

Many Indian women⁹ have reported that they are taught to feel ashamed and discouraged from talking about any kind of stomach related, gas or bowel problems as its considered shameful or disrespectful by many families, this may also be due to a taboo related with menstruation which is another task in plate. Therefore, behaviour like these discourages open discussion and results in lack of help seeking behaviour⁹. Moreover, government programmes and non-governmental organizations usually create awareness about communicable diseases like T.B., AIDS etc or non-communicable diseases like cardiovascular disease, diabetes, nutrient deficiency diseases etc. and IBS is rarely a part of any of these campaigns. Another key challenge is that IBS is often thought as a minor digestion problem due to poor eating habits and rarely regarded as a chronic health issue which can affect the work-life balance¹⁰ and quality of life. Indian population who are suffering from IBS often get confused and overlap it with other ailments and then try home remedies like churn or go for over-the-counter Ayurvedic, Homeopathic or Unani medicine instead of visiting a doctor. Also, talks like how mental health can influence your gut health are still very unfamiliar topics by majority of Indians¹⁰. Many general practitioners in remote and rural areas may not be trained properly to identify and diagnose IBS thus resulting in underreporting among Indians. In India the mass media such as television, newspaper, social media is highly focussed with weight loss regime and beauty tips programmes, neglecting awareness about several major health problems including irritable bowel syndrome. In India, IBS has failed to become a part of even social-media discussions such a live fitness shows, podcasts etc. As there is no test to indicate IBS, and it's basically diagnosed by exclusion and following Rome-IV criteria which is understood by medical professionals but seen as doubt

or suspicion by common people, often disbelieved or mis-understood by them. Another important challenge is language barrier as many languages are read, spoken and written in India, 22 of which are officially recognized, it becomes even more challenging to create awareness even among the educated people as most of the modern medicine text is available in English language (Mantha, S. 2023, Feb 7).

What can be done?

Here are some suggestions for tackling this challenge in India some of which can also be incorporated around the world. There is a need to launch national awareness campaign just like those for tuberculosis or cancer etc. so that talks about gut health can be normalized. Government platforms (like My Gov, Arogya Setu etc.), social media and NGO's must play a significant role in spreading right information about IBS. Using mass media like television, YouTube adds, posters, skits/play at public forums can be very helpful and engaging. It's important to consider India regional and linguistic diversity and accordingly create educational awareness packages so that they are readily accepted and easily understood by local people. Add basic digestive issues and mental health related topics in school curriculum so that it reduces stigma at an early age and dialogue about this creates a free environment to talk about it. Continuous training programs and awareness campaigns should also be conducted for the healthcare providers living in the rural areas or remote areas especially at primary health care centres (PHC). Government should encourage traditional and modern medical practitioners to work together as traditional medicine is widely trusted by huge Indian population. Some helpline numbers can be created, which can be handled by trained IBS counsellors thus maintaining confidentiality and privacy of the patients in relatively conservative parts of India. More fund should be provided for research in the field of IBS with reference to the special conditions of our country in terms of awareness, socio economic status, cultural differences, food preferences, mental health challenges, quality of

life etc. Collaboration among major health institutions like AIIMS, PGI, KGMC etc. can play a crucial role in fulfilling this challenge by conducting online/offline seminars, conferences, campaigning, training programmes etc. regarding IBS awareness. Finally, integrated management of IBS involving mental health awareness, role of diet, association with physical activity should all be handled together for the holistic benefit of the IBS patients. In the end I would like to conclude by saying that it's time to handle silence with support and stigma with science.

References:

1. von dem Knesebeck, O., Löwe, B., Lüdecke, D., Bobardt, J. S., and Barbek, R., Public knowledge and beliefs about the irritable bowel syndrome - results from the SOMA.SOC study. *BMC Public Health*, 2024, **24**, 1–8.
2. Mathias, E. G., Dhyani, V. S., Krishnan, J. B., Rani, U., Gudi, N., and Pattanshetty, S., Community based health literacy interventions in India: A scoping review. *Clin. Epidemiol. Glob. Heal.*, 2023, **22**, 101310.
3. Gao, X., Tian, S., Huang, N., Sun, G., and Huang, T., Associations of daily sedentary behavior, physical activity, and sleep with irritable bowel syndrome: A prospective analysis of 362,193 participants. *J. Sport Heal. Sci.*, 2023, 1–9.
4. Baig, M., Gazzaz, Z. J., Alyoubi, W. E., et al., Knowledge, Awareness, and Prevalence of Irritable Bowel Syndrome in the Saudi Community: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Cureus*, 2024, **16**, 1–10.
5. Yao, X., Yang, Y., Zhang, S., Shi, Y., Zhang, Q., and Wang, Y., The impact of overlapping functional dyspepsia, belching disorders and functional heartburn on anxiety, depression and quality of life of Chinese patients with irritable bowel syndrome. *BMC Gastroenterol.*, 2020, **20**, 1–8.

6. Tack, J., Stanghellini, V., Mearin, F., et al., Economic burden of moderate to severe irritable bowel syndrome with constipation in six European countries. *BMC Gastroenterol.*, 2019, **19**.
7. Rahman, M. M., Mahadeva, S., and Ghoshal, U. C., Epidemiological and clinical perspectives on irritable bowel syndrome in India, Bangladesh and Malaysia: A review. *World J. Gastroenterol.*, 2017, **23**, 6788–6801.
8. Lovell, R. M. and Ford, A. C., Global Prevalence of and Risk Factors for Irritable Bowel Syndrome: A Meta-analysis. *Clin. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.*, 2012, **10**, 712-721.e4.
9. Kim, Y. S. and Kim, N., Sex-gender differences in irritable bowel syndrome. *J. Neurogastroenterol. Motil.*, 2018, **24**, 544–558.
10. Saroj, S. and Gupta, K., Effect of Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) Symptoms on the work-life balance of females: A comparative study. *Indian J. Home Sci.*, 2023, **35**, 289–302.